

APPENDIX S2

Materials and Methods – Complete Details

Taxon Selection

We sampled 24 of the 26-28 Pseudocrenilabrinae tribes. The only missing riverine tribe was the monotypic Coelotilapiini for which no tissues were available to us. The two or three (depending on classification scheme) other unrepresented tribes were the monogeneric Hemibatini, Trematocarini and Benthochromini of Lake Tanganyika. Aside from these, most Tanganyikan and EAR lineages were represented. We also sampled taxa from endemic species flocks of the lower Congo River (*Lamprologus*, *Nanochromis*, *Steatocranus*, *Teleogramma*), crater lakes Barombi Mbo and Bermin, Lake Fwa, and soda lakes Natron and Magadi. Only a handful of Lake Malawi and Lake Victoria species were incorporated since these represent closely related clades nested well within Haplochromini (Friedman et al. 2013; Matschiner et al. 2017; Meyer et al. 2015; Irisarri et al. 2018), and thus additional taxa would contribute little to the resolution of higher-level Pseudocrenilabrinae relationships. For polytypic tribes and genera we sampled two or more genera and species, respectively. Quotation marks are used to denote taxa awaiting formal description or whose current generic assignment is questionable. Quotations are also applied to generic names for species that fall outside of the clade containing the type species for that genus in our analyses. Given the support for monophyly of the currently informally designated chromidotilapiines (Schwarzer et al. 2015) and pelmatochromines (Schwarzer et al. 2011; Dunz & Schlieven 2013) we herein recognize them as tribes (Chromidotilapiini and Pelmatochromini). Tribal assemblages are referred to using the suffix “ines” (e.g., haplotilapiines).

Pseudocrenilabrinae was placed in a broader phylogenetic context with the inclusion of representatives from the remaining cichlid subfamilies (Cichlinae, Etroplinae, Ptychochrominae) and 11 additional families from within Blenniiformes (*sensu* Ghezelayagh et al. 2021, formerly Ovalentaria). Blenniiformes were selected based on their close relationship to cichlids in previous studies, with a particular focus on testing the proposed sister relationship of Pholidichthyidae and Cichlidae (Wainwright et al. 2012; Near et al. 2013; Friedman et al. 2013; Eytan et al. 2015; Betancur-R et al. 2017). Taxonomic names applied for non-cichlid Blenniiformes were in keeping with recent classification updates for teleostean fishes (Betancur-R et al. 2017; Ghezelayagh et al. 2021). In total our dataset included 178 terminals, with 165 cichlid (Pseudocrenilabrinae: 150, Cichlinae: 3, Etroplinae: 5, Ptychochrominae: 7) and 13 non-cichlid Blenniiformes species. Information and summary statistics for taxa and loci are available in Tables S1-S5.

DNA Extraction, Library Preparation and Sequencing

Genomic DNA was extracted from muscle tissue and fin clips preserved in 90%-95% ethanol using the DNeasy Blood and Tissue kit (Qiagen, Venlo, the Netherlands). The standard manufacturer's protocol was followed with two minor modifications. First, 4 μ L of RNase A (Qiagen) was added in the first step of extraction to aid in the digestion of RNA. Second, for the final elution 50 μ L ddH₂O was added two times, instead of a single addition of 200 μ L Buffer AE solution. DNA content was assessed by visualizing extractions on a 1.5% agarose gel stained with SYBR safe. Samples with a single discernible band were selected for DNA sequencing.

Library preparation and sequencing were performed at the University of Toronto Donnelly Sequencing Centre (<http://dsc.utoronto.ca/dsc/index.html>). A set of 923 probes, designed based on a Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) reference genome (from BioMart Ensembl Genes 69

database; Flicek et al. 2013), was used for targeted sequence capture of putative single-copy exons (Ilves & López-Fernández 2014). Loci were selected for bait design based on the following criteria: (1) 750-2000 bp in length to ensure adequate phylogenetic signal; (2) denoted as protein coding on the Ensembl database; (3) annotated with a specific gene name or description; (4) returned a single hit when compared against the Nile tilapia genome with NCBI's BLAST tool (Altschul et al. 1990); (5) also returned a single hit when BLASTed against four additional cichlid genomes; (6) absence of extensive indels or repeats. Probe efficacy was ascertained through their ability to capture sequences and infer the "known" cichlid family backbone in a phylogeny of ten taxa. The target set included 32 opsin sequences intended for use in other studies. Opsins were removed from our dataset due to widespread duplication and pseudogenization in visual pigment genes (Bowmaker 2008; Cortesi et al. 2015). High-throughput sequencing was performed using an Illumina HiSeq platform with paired-end sequencing. Complete details of probe design, library preparation and exon capture protocols are available from Ilves & López-Fernández (2014).

Sequence Processing: From Reads to Exons

Paired-end sequence reads were processed to yield target exons using a custom bioinformatics pipeline adapted from Ilves et al. (2018). Raw reads were first sorted, filtered and trimmed to ensure that only those meeting certain quality thresholds were retained. Reads that were < 60 bp in length, contained > 1% ambiguous bases, exhibited a mean quality score < 20 and represented duplicates of any type (exact, reverse, 3'/5' end duplicates) were filtered out. Poly-A/T tails ≥ 5 bp in length and bases with a mean score < 20 (assessed using a sliding window of 5 with step size 1) were trimmed from the 3' and 5' ends. All quality control measures were implemented with prinseq version 0.20.3 lite (Schmieder & Edwards 2011).

The remaining high-quality reads were mapped to tilapia reference sequences and assembled into target exons using Bowtie2 2.2.0 (Langmead & Salzberg 2012) with a maximum fragment length for paired-end alignments of 600 bp and the --very-sensitive-local preset. This preset specifies a maximum of 20 seed extension attempts, a re-seeding value of three, zero allowable mismatches in a seed alignment and parameters for a function governing the interval between seed substrings. Resulting SAM files were converted to sorted BAM files with SAMtools 0.1.19 (Li et al. 2009). Consensus exon sequences were generated from sorted BAM files using the SAMtools mpileup and vcfutils functions, for which minimum mapping quality, base quality and read depth values of 20, 20 and 10 were specified, respectively. Output FASTQ files were converted to consensus FASTA files with the SeqIO.convert function in Biopython 1.68 (Cock et al. 2009). A custom script (Appendix G in Ilves et al. 2018) was used to convert low quality bases to N's and to trim 3'/5' N tails. Consensus sequences < 100 bp in length were further excluded.

Exon Assembly for Non-Cichlid Blenniiformes, Etroplinae and Ptychochrominae

Blenniiformes outgroups and Indo-Malagasy subfamilies (Etroplinae and Ptychochrominae) exhibited more missing data than African and Neotropical cichlids, with generally lower alignment rates and fewer target sequence bp (Fig. S2, Tables S3-S4). Reduced data recovery was probably related to these lineages last sharing a common ancestor with the tilapia reference deeper in time than African or Neotropical cichlids. Some data loss likely occurred during target capture, but lower alignment rates suggest that additional loss occurred during the assembly of target exons. Accumulated mutations in these taxa seem to have interfered with alignment of reads to the tilapia reference during guided assembly. Therefore, we applied a

modified assembly protocol aimed at increasing bp yield for these taxa, thus achieving a more uniform locus set across samples.

We used a hybrid reference guided/*de novo* assembly approach for a subset of Etroplinae and Ptychochrominae. Hybrid assembly proved to be computationally intensive, and since our focus was on resolving Pseudocrenilabrinae relationships, hybrid assembly was restricted to the seven (of 12) Etroplinae and Ptychochrominae that had the lowest sequence recovery relative to all Cichlinae. A similar but less intensive reduced-sensitivity approach was applied for the remaining five Etroplinae/Ptychochrominae species with lower levels of missing data and the 13 outgroup taxa (Fig. S2, see also Table S4 for taxon-specific designation of assembly approach).

Hybrid assembly consisted of three stages (Fig. S3, Appendix S3). The first stage (Fig. S3b) was a guided assembly, in which reads were mapped to the tilapia references in BWA-MEM 0.7.12 (Li & Durbin 2009; Li 2013) with less stringent mapping parameters than the `--very-sensitive-local` pre-set in Bowtie2. Read mapping was improved with a seed length of 17, re-seeding value of 0.25, matching score of two and a mismatch penalty of two. Consensus sequences were generated with SAMtools and Biopython as for all other cichlids, except that a read depth of six, instead of 10, was specified. In the second stage (Fig. S3c), exons were re-assembled, this time *de novo*, using the Velvet 1.0.17 assembler (Zehrino & Birney 2008). *De novo* contigs were obtained by assembling reads under a range of kmer values between 19-61 and then combining these into a final set of longer contigs with the AssemblyAssembler1.3 Python script (Crawford 2010). Reads corresponding to the final contig set were identified with the `extractContigReads.pl` script (Zehrino 2009) and used to inform SAMtool's filtering of contigs with read depth < 6. The remaining contigs were grouped by species and matched to their corresponding exons in the indexed tilapia reference using BWA. In the third and final stage (Fig. S3d), guided and *de novo*

assembled exons were aligned to each other using MUSCLE v3.8.31 (Edgar 2004) with default parameters. These alignments were imported into Geneious 7.0.6 (<http://www.geneious.com>, Kearse et al. 2012), where they were individually assessed and manually edited where necessary. Editing involved the removal of artificially introduced gaps and shifting of misaligned sequences. Most alignments exhibited a combination of sections recovered in both guided and *de novo* assemblies as well as sections recovered only by *de novo* assembly. Sections recovered by both approaches were identical, suggesting that regions of an exon derived exclusively from *de novo* assembly were also accurately recovered. Consensus exon sequences were generated by combining their guided and *de novo* assembled contigs. In this way, *de novo* assembly extended exons along sections that could not be readily mapped back to the tilapia reference with guided assembly alone. Known coding regions and codon positions (see next section) were used to confirm that hybrid assembly did not disrupt open reading frames.

The reduced-sensitivity approach applied to a few Etroplinae/Ptychochrominae cichlids and the non-cichlid outgroups was equivalent to the first stage of hybrid assembly. Targeted high-throughput sequencing has proven especially difficult for *Pholidichthys*, with previous phylogenomic attempts resulting in reduced sequence recovery relative to other taxa in the same dataset (Eytan et al. 2015; pers. obs.). We sequenced three *Pholidichthys* individuals, each of which showed reduced data recovery relative to most other taxa (Table S4). It remains unclear whether these challenges are due to poor sample quality and/or sequence divergence. Regardless, we aimed to maximize the number of phylogenetically informative sites for assessing the Pholidichthyidae+Cichlidae sister relationship in a phylogenomic context. For each exon, sequences from the three individuals were combined into a single *Pholidichthys* consensus sequence (see Tables S1 and S4 for individual and consensus sequence information). We ensured

that exons from different individuals were correctly aligned for consensus-generation by ascertaining that sections recovered in at least two individuals exhibited identical bp.

Hybrid guided/*de novo* and reduced-sensitivity assembly approaches resulted in a significant increase in sequence recovery for the Indo-Malagasy cichlids and outgroup taxa compared to initial assembly attempts with Bowtie2 ($t(16506.1) = 40.0, p = 0.0$; Fig. S4). The span of target sequences relative to their corresponding references increased by a mean of 16.8 +/- 22.7%, and 1,624,734 bp and 1087 exons were added across taxa. The greatest improvements in data recovery were obtained with the hybrid approach. Hybrid assembly increased the span of target sequences by a mean of 21.1 +/- 22.9% compared to 15.2 +/- 22.4% with the reduced-sensitivity approach ($t(4441.6) = 11.0, p = 0.0$). New exons were added with both approaches either by generating contigs for loci that were not represented in Bowtie2 assemblies or by extending loci that initially spanned only a small portion of their reference such that they met the minimum threshold for inclusion in phylogenetic analyses. Hybrid assembly contributed a mean of 52.4 +/- 5.5 new exons per species, more than the 42.4 +/- 13.4 exons per species added with the reduced-sensitivity approach ($t(22.0) = 2.6, p = 0.01$). A total of 367 new exons and 537,275 bp were added across the seven Etroplinae/Ptychochrominae cichlids, and 942 new exons and 1,087,459 bp across the outgroup and five Etroplinae/Ptychochrominae taxa. See Tables S1-S4 for additional taxa and exon summary statistics.

Identifying Coding and Non-Coding Regions

Recent (2016) updates to the annotated Nile tilapia genome on GenBank (NCBI *Oreochromis niloticus* Annotation Release 103; Accession No. GCF_001858045.1) revealed that some of Ilves and López-Fernández's (2014) original targets included non-coding regions. We

retrieved updated mRNA sequences for *Oreochromis niloticus* from GenBank (Clark et al. 2016) and used these to identify coding/non-coding regions and codon positions in the corresponding targets (see Appendix S4 for custom script; Altschul et al. 1990; Maglott et al. 2005; R Core Team 2015). Knowledge of these sites in our targets helped to inform alignment editing and data partitioning for model selection (see next two sections).

Exon Alignments

Exon sequences were aligned using MUSCLE with default parameters and then imported into Geneious where they were reviewed and manually edited to ensure homology where necessary. Sequences for taxa that were obviously misaligned with others in the same exon alignment (e.g., due to extended repeat regions or localized substitutions) were shifted towards the 3' or 5' ends to maximize the percent of matching sites across taxa. Gaps introduced during alignment were deleted to ensure the retention of open reading frames. Finally 3' and 5' ends with missing or ambiguous data (i.e., gaps or N's) across more than half of taxa within an alignment were trimmed, as these regions are expected to contribute more noise than informative sites during phylogenetic inference.

Alignments exhibited differing amounts of missing data in the form of unsampled taxa and missing characters (i.e., incomplete sequences). Simulation and empirical investigations have shown that the inclusion of taxa and loci with even large amounts of missing data are unlikely to be problematic and may even improve phylogenetic estimates when a large number of informative characters are sampled overall (Wiens & Morrill 2011; Jiang et al. 2014; Xi et al. 2016; Nute et al. 2018). Accordingly, a limited amount of missing taxonomic and character data was permitted. Within each alignment, taxa spanning less than 30% (i.e., non-gap and non-N characters) of the

corresponding tilapia reference were eliminated. Alignments whose remaining taxon count was at least 70% of the total (i.e., at least 124 of 178 species) were retained for phylogenetic analyses. In addition to individual exon alignments, a supermatrix was generated for concatenated analyses.

Data Partitions

Data partitioning and model selection were performed on individual exon alignments and the supermatrix. Individual exon alignments were partitioned by coding and non-coding regions as well as first, second and third codon positions. The supermatrix was partitioned by exon, and by coding and non-coding regions, as it was too large to also differentiate codon positions. The best partition schemes and evolutionary models were identified using PartitionFinder v1.1.1 (Lanfear et al. 2012) with branchlengths = unlinked, models = raxml (Lanfear et al. 2014), model_selection = BIC and search = all specified.

PartitionFinder confirmed that, despite the large number of exons and presence of coding and non-coding regions, a single data block was most appropriate for individual exon alignments and the supermatrix. The GTR+G model was the best fit for the supermatrix, and either the GTR+G or GTR+G+I for individual exons. The GTR+G model was used for all exons, as it has been suggested that the G parameter already accounts for sites with very low mutation rates while the inclusion of the I parameter makes it difficult to accurately estimate the gamma distribution and proportion of invariant sites (Yang 2006 and references therein).

Phylogenetic Inference: Concatenation

We inferred species relationships with traditional maximum likelihood (ML) concatenation analysis on the supermatrix. Analyses were undertaken in the CIPRES Science Gateway (Miller

et al. 2010) using RAxML-HPC v.8 on XSEDE (8.2.10) (Stamatakis 2014). Rapid bootstrapping, the GTR+G model and 1000 bootstrap replicates were specified. We also performed concatenated analyses on a subset of Bowtie2 assembled core loci to confirm that using variably-assembled loci (i.e., Bowtie2, hybrid guided/*de novo* and reduced-sensitivity) did not bias topological findings by The variably-assembled and core loci topologies were congruent, with slightly lowered bootstrap values in the core loci tree (results not shown).

Phylogenetic Inference: Species Tree

We inferred relationships while accounting for gene heterogeneity under ILS using species tree approaches. ML gene trees were obtained from exon alignments using raxmlHPC-MPI-SSE3 v8.2.8 with rapid bootstrapping, the GTR+G model and 1000 bootstrap replicates. The species tree was estimated from the best scoring gene trees and with 700 multilocus bootstrap replicates in ASTRAL-II v.4.10.8 (Mirarab & Warnow 2015). Local posterior probabilities, alternative quartet support and gene concordance factors (Fig. S8) were also calculated to assess topological robustness under different support measures and to quantify gene heterogeneity at each node. Posterior probabilities and alternative quartet support were computed on the inferred species tree in ASTRAL-II with the ML gene trees and -t 3 and -t 8 parameters. Node-specific gene tree conflict was visualized with pie charts, in which slices represent gene tree support for the three possible quartet topologies. Pies were generated with ape 5.0's "nodelabels" function (Paradis & Schliep 2019) with the "pie" object equal to ASTRAL's q1-q3 support values (full numerical annotations available in Appendix S7). Gene concordance factors were computed as an additional measure of genetic incongruence in IQ-TREE 2 (Minh et al. 2020).

Summary species tree methods, like ASTRAL, are influenced by resolution of the gene trees on which they are based. Therefore we investigated the informativeness of our loci and the impacts of alternate treatments of input ML gene trees on ASTRAL analyses. We summarized parsimony informative sites in IQ-TREE 1.6.12 (Nguyen et al. 2015). We also quantified the informativeness of our loci across tree depths (i.e., from family to genus levels) by analyzing node support for gene trees. Each gene tree was rooted with non-cichlid Blenniiformes, as in concatenated and species trees, and made ultrametric with the “cladogram” option in FigTree v1.4.3 (Rambaut 2012). Each gene tree was then subdivided into quarters based on tree depth starting from the root (i.e., 25%, 50%, 75% and 100% of total tree depth) in R. Making gene trees ultrametric ensured that the deepest quarters comprise most higher order (e.g., familial to intertribal) relationships, while the final depths consist primarily of lower order (e.g., intrageneric) divergences. Mean bootstrap support was computed across nodes within each quarter and also for nodes within the last 20% of tree depth (i.e., nodes closest to the tip). We also assessed the impacts of exon length on gene tree resolution, since shorter loci have potentially fewer phylogenetically informative characters and are prone to estimation error. Exons were sorted into nine length-specific bins, each with a range of 200bp (i.e., 200-400, ... 1801-2000 bp). Mean bootstrap support across gene trees was then computed for each bin.

We considered the impacts of systematic gene tree error on the species tree by repeating ASTRAL analyses with three alternative sets of gene trees. First, we aimed to minimize the influence of poorly-resolved, and potentially erroneously inferred, topologies by collapsing gene tree nodes with bootstrap values less than 10 in R’s `ips` 0.0.11 package (Heibl 2008). We selected a cut-off of 10% based on previous studies indicating this to be a reasonable threshold for datasets of a comparable size (Mirarab & Warnow 2015, Zhang et al. 2018). ASTRAL analyses were then

performed using these ML gene trees with collapsed low-support nodes. We assessed whether model misspecification could have affected results. We re-estimated ML gene trees with the GTR+G+I model for the selection of loci identified by PartitionFinder. The ASTRAL species tree was then inferred once more, this time with a combination of gene trees based on either the GTR+G or GTR+G+ models (Table S2). We tested for a common source of model misspecification, base compositional heterogeneity (Foster 2004), using a X^2 test in IQ-TREE. We also used IQ-TREE to reassess the fit of over 200 alternative substitution models not implemented in RAxML, and to generate ML gene trees based on these newly identified best-fit models (Table S2) to serve as input for ASTRAL analysis. The three alternative ASTRAL species trees were compared with the weighted Robinson-Foulds distance (Robinson & Foulds 1981), as implemented in R's phangorn 2.8.1 package (Schliep 2011) and visualized with the comparePhylo function in ape (Fig. S5).

Phylogenetic Inference: Hybrid Network Analyses

We tested for historical hybridization and assessed its impacts on Pseudocrenilabrinae relationships using SNaQ phylogenetic networks analyses implemented in PhyloNetworks (Bezanson et al. 2015, Solís-Lemus et al. 2017). Performing SNaQ analyses on the complete set of taxa and loci was computational unfeasible. Instead, we focused on eight taxonomic subsets to assess hybridization at various phylogenetic scales. For each subset, ASTRAL species and ML gene trees were pruned to a selection of representative species. ML gene trees were further filtered to retain only those containing all species in the corresponding subset.

Sub1 (16 species, 497 gene trees) sampled most (16 of 23) Pseudocrenilabrinae tribes to test for deep hybridization events. Sub2 (13 species, 437 gene trees) investigated hybridization amongst the earliest diverging WCA lineages. Sub3 (11 species, 433 gene trees) investigated

hybrid networks within the largest WCA tribe, Chromidotilapiini. The remaining subsets focused on the pan-African haplotilapiines. Sub4 (10 species, 580 gene trees) considered hybridization amongst former-tilapiine tribes. Sub5 (15 species, 555 gene trees) assessed hybrid networks within the Barombi Mbo, Bermin and Natron/Magadi flocks, and between these and their close riverine relatives. Sub6 (21 species, 520 gene trees) sampled former-tilapiine and EAR lineages to look for deep hybridization between EAR and non-EAR lineages. Sub7 (20 species, 512 gene trees) sampled all available EAR tribes for a more thorough assessment of hybridization within the EAR clade. Sub8 (14 species, 489 gene trees) looked for hybridization within Lamprologini and between Lamprologini and its close former-tilapiine and H-lineage relatives.

For each subset, SNaQ analyses were performed iteratively, with increasing hybridization thresholds (h_{\max}) and 20 runs. In the first iteration, the ASTRAL species tree was used as the starting tree and an $h_{\max} = 0$ was specified. Successive iterations were conducted with $h_{\max} = n+1$ and the best scoring (lowest log pseudolikelihood) network from the previous search as the starting topology, until scores stabilized (when drop in log pseudolikelihood was less than two). Support for hybrid networks was assessed with 100 bootstrap replicates per subset.

Tree Spaces: Comparison of Concatenated, Species and Hybrid Network Topologies

We compared the topologies of our concatenated (Fig. S6), species (Fig. 2 in main text), hybrid network (Fig. 3 in main text) and gene trees by inferring multivariate “tree spaces”. The position of trees in these tree spaces were based on two distance metrics, as implemented in the R package treespace 1.1.4.1 (Jombart et al. 2017). The Kendall-Colijn metric computes Euclidean distances between trees based on the number of edges on the path from the root to the most recent common ancestor for all tip pairs (Kendal & Colijn 2016). The tip-tip path difference metric is the

square root of the sum of squares of pairwise differences, which are calculated as the difference in number of edges between each pair of tips (Steel & Penny 1993). We limited comparisons to topological differences, since branch lengths are not equivalent. Branch lengths in ML (concatenated and gene) and species trees reflect accumulated bp differences and amount of genetic discordance across gene trees, respectively.

First, we inferred a tree space that compared the entire Pseudocrenilabrinae topology, which excluded hybrid networks, as these were based on subsets of taxa. We also generated additional tree spaces that encompassed taxa included in each of the hybrid networks. For these analyses concatenated, species and gene trees were pruned down to the selection of taxa included in each subset. In all cases, only gene trees that included all taxa within the given tree space were included, since the distance metrics used require identical tips across the trees being compared. Tree spaces based on the Kendall-Colijn and tip-tip path difference metrics produced comparable results (Fig. S7).

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Figure S2. Read alignment and sequence recovery statistics for taxa based on initial target assembly with the Bowtie2 very-sensitive-local pre-set. Summary statistics are calculated across taxa for each of the specified taxon groups. Statistics for the outgroups and two sets of Indo-Malagasy cichlids are shown separately from other cichlids in order to highlight differences in initial data recovery. Based on these differences, alternative assembly approaches (i.e., hybrid guided/*de novo* or reduced-sensitivity) were subsequently used to improve target assembly for the outgroups and Indo-Malagasy taxa. a) Proportion of reads aligned to the corresponding reference during guided assembly. b) Total number of exons that spanned a minimum of 30% of their reference. c) Mean percent span of exons relative to their corresponding references.

Figure S3. Diagrammatical representation of our hybrid guided/*de novo* assembly approach. This schematic shows the assembly process from reads to consensus sequence for a single exon belonging to one species. The three stages of the hybrid approach are separated into three labelled boxes. a) Raw data consists of the Nile Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) reference and the set of sequencing reads for the target exon being assembled. b) Stage 1: guided assembly of raw reads with the Tilapia reference. c) Stage 2: *de novo* assembly of raw reads. d) Stage 3: alignment and extraction of consensus sequences from guided and *de novo* assembled reads. The origin and head of arrows indicate the input data and output product for each stage of the process. Letters adjacent to arrows represent the tools used at each

stage: A) BWA-MEM; B) SAMtools, Biopython's SeqIQ.conver; C) Velvet, AssemblyAssembler1.3, extractContigReads.pl; D) bowtie2; E) SAMtools, Biopython's SeqIQ.conver; F) BWA-MEM; G) MUSCLE; H) Geneious. See Appendix S3 for scripts. *Katria katria* illustration by Viviana Astudillo-Clavijo.

Figure S4. Improved sequence recovery for the Etroplinae, Ptychochrominae and non-cichlid Blenniiformes outgroup taxa. Percent Difference records the difference in the span of target sequences relative to their corresponding references between the Bowtie2 and improved-recovery assembly approaches. Mean percent difference is shown for each taxa by the coloured circles. Percent differences for the three *Pholidichthys sp.* individuals are summarized with a single boxplot (see Table S4 for individual values and additional summary statistics).

a)

b)

c)

Figure S5. Alternative ASTRAL species trees based on different sets of input gene trees. a) Species tree based on gene trees with low-support ($< 10\%$ bootstrap) branches collapsed. b) Species tree based on gene trees estimated with either the GTR+G or GTR+G+I model. c) Species tree based on gene trees estimated using alternative best-fit models in IQ-TREE. Red circles indicate nodes that differ from those in the final tree (Fig. 2 in main text).

Figure S6. Concatenation phylogeny for Pseudocrenilabrinae and close relatives. a) Concatenated phylogeny with branch lengths reflecting accumulated mutations. Bootstrap support values less than 90 are shown in red. b) Concatenated cladogram with branch lengths adjusted to improve legibility of support values. All bootstrap values are shown, with those less 90 in red.

Figure S7. Tree spaces comparing *Pseudocrenilabrinae* hypotheses across concatenated, species, hybrid network and gene trees based on the Kendall-Colijn metric. a) Comparison of full phylogeny across concatenated, species and gene trees. b-i) Comparison of concatenated, species, hybrid network and gene trees, restricted to taxa in hybrid network subsets.

Figure S8. ASTRAL species tree with node annotations showing gene concordance factor.